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Bureaucracy and Organisational Productivity in Nigeria's Public Organisations: A Study of the Port Harcourt Refining Company

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ABSTRACT

Using the Port Harcourt Refining Company as a case, this study attempted to unravel the factors that limit the capacity of the bureaucracy with regards to achieving optimal productivity in Nigeria's public organisations. The background to this study acknowledged the fact that in any politically independent society, public organisations or establishments exist as instruments through which the government directly administers socio-economic needs to the citizenry and also generate revenue. However, in the Nigerian situation, public organisations or firms, by virtue of their unproductive status, constitute liabilities instead of being dependably instrumental to generating revenue for the government and providing essential but quality social services to the Nigerian people. The study raised three research questions to aid its scientific inquiries. It utilised the instruments of questionnaires as the primary source of data collection, as well as textbooks, journals, and materials from the internet as secondary sources. The study was anchored on the theory of structural functionalism. Findings from the study revealed that political/bureaucratic corruption, bureaucratic red-tape, technical/administrative incompetence and indiscriminate political interferences on the functions of public servants, constitute the factors that are responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve an appreciable level of productivity in the management of public organisations in Nigeria. Conclusively, this study impressed that for the Nigerian state to attain a socio-economic height that would reflect in having very viable and productive public organisations, the bureaucratic system needs an intensive overhauling. To this end, the study recommended among other things, that there should be a public-private partnership restructuring strategy to boost both technical and administrative competence in the bureaucracy.

Keywords: Administration, Statutory, Organisational Structure, Productivity, Management

INTRODUCTION

Fundamentally, organisations are established for a definite purpose of realising relevant objectives on regular basis. The actualisation of the said objectives is tied to the dutiful performance of tasks. Organisational tasks in this context generally include the various functions and activities which are carried out to sustain the primary aim of achieving the objectives of the firm. Invariably, the fulfilment or realisation of set goals or proposed objectives is a product of the impact of guiding laws, principles and policies. The said policies or laws, under normal circumstances must reflect strategies, tactics and methods aimed at accomplishing tasks and achieving objectives. Any formal organisation, whether private or public in structure, which establishment is primarily anchored on objective realisation or goals accomplishment must function with laid down rules, policies and principles. The survival, successes and

optimal performance of an organisation, in most part, depend on the nature or pattern of applicability of organisational methods and strategies. In comparative terms, performance rating among competing firms is usually measured and determined by the effectiveness of organizational strategies or methods (Eneagu, 2021; Ishaya, 2023).

Undoubtedly, the day-to-day running of an organisation is a function or basic responsibility which is vested in the management. Management in this context may comprise an individual or body of individuals who are usually saddled with the administrative task of effectively utilising both the material and human resources at the disposal of the organisation towards organisational goals accomplishment. In private organisations, full management roles could be undertaken by an individual, especially with regards to smaller business outfits. Still under private organizational structures, corporate firms would always have their management undertaken by Boards of Directors. In this circumstance, elements of bureaucratic protocols are usually observed in the course of setting of goals, formulation of policies and strategies, as well as in the aspect of decision making. However, unlike in public organisations, decision making is usually swifter, more precise, comprehensive and passionately executed. Such, in most cases, leads to greater productive output (Mayowa, 2019).

Public organisations in Nigeria are established for the primary purpose of providing essential social services to the masses. In addition to this, public organisations or corporations in Nigeria exist as sources of generating revenues for the purpose of executing the overall task of governance or general administration. The various tasks of governance or general administration in this context must necessarily entail among other things, the provision and maintenance of physical and social infrastructural development, periodic remuneration of political office holders, civil servants in various ministries, as well as pensioners and the maintenance of diplomatic relations. However, it has been widely observed that the bureaucracy, over the years, has performed below standard with regards to the management of public organisations in Nigeria (Isodeke, 2020). According to Akpan (2020), the seemingly remarkable distinction in productivity output between public and private organisations is prompted by the difference and peculiarity in the method of administration. Thus, while there is a commendably high level of managerial competence, commitment, flexibility, forthrightness and dedication in the management of private enterprises, such is contrasted in public organisations where there is in existence, a high level of manifest incompetence, rigidity, low level of commitment, irresoluteness, apathy and nonchalant attitude to work. Therefore, using the Port Harcourt Refining Company, Rivers State, this study aims at ascertaining the factors responsible for bureaucratic limitations with regards to achieving a commendably high level of productivity in Nigeria's public organisations. The study developed three research questions to aid the research investigation. They include:

- I. What are the factors responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve optimal productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company?
- II. What are the consequences of the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve optimal productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining Company?
- III. What strategies can be adopted to improve the capacity of the bureaucracy to effectively achieve productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The study adopted both the survey and qualitative research designs as the guiding plan for the purpose of gathering reliable data. The study generated data from respondents in the field of study, on the factors responsible for the ineffectiveness of the bureaucracy to achieve a high level of productivity in public organisations, using selected public organisations as case. The study also generated data from the reviewed works of other scholars as well as data from official sources.

Population of the Study: The population of the study is made up of the entire staff strength of the Port Harcourt Refining Company, Rivers State. The current staff strength of the Port Harcourt is 485 (Oyedeji, 2022).

Sample and Sample Technique: This study used the purposive sampling technique to determine the sampled respondents, as well as the sampled size. Out of the 450 population, this study purposively selected 420. Using the purposive method, the study deliberately excluded some categories of workers from participating in the study. These workers include those on both annual and sick leave, workers with considerably poor educational background workers who exhibited early signs of indifference to the research exercise.

Nature/Sources of Data: This study relied on both the primary and secondary sources to generate sufficient data on the role of bureaucracy in achieving productivity in public organisations in Nigeria. The primary data were generated from the Port Harcourt Refining Company- the latter which is the field of study, while the secondary data were generated through literature review.

Method of Data Collection: This study administered 420 questionnaires to the sampled respondents selected at the Port Harcourt Refining Company. Also, the study instrumentalised textbooks, journals and materials from the internet as the secondary sources of generating data.

Method of Data Presentation/Analysis: Data from fieldwork were presented in table and results interpreted in simple percentages. The data from questionnaire responses were presented in a four-Likert scale and interpreted in simple percentages. The study used both the quantitative and qualitative data analysis method.

Conceptual Review

Bureaucracy

The term ‘bureaucracy’ was coined from both old French and Latin words; “bureau” and “Kratos or cracy”. While the word “bureau” signifies writing desk, the Latin word “Kratos or cracy” denotes “power” or power to rule. Therefore, the word “bureaucracy” is translated in English language to mean “the statutory and legitimate official powers to make rules and direct actions. Bureaucracy is generally considered as an idea which is broadly and intensively practiced in the field of Public Administration. This, unarguably can be attributed to the strategic, incalculable, vital and indispensable position bureaucracy plays in the routine administration of the society, state or organisational structures. Bureaucracy exists in both private and public organisations. It essentially involves a body of individuals who are saddled with the official responsibilities of making rules, establishing standards, designing organisational strategies and systematically executing decisions for the purpose of sustaining the growth and survival of the organisation or society, as well as realising determined objectives. However, while bureaucracy in private organisations entails the strategic application of company policies by management committee members or board of directors of private firms or corporations, bureaucracy in public organisations denotes the exercise of implementation of policies and programmes, as well as other aspects of administrative functions by government-employed civil/public servants in the various Ministries, Agencies, Parastatals or enterprises of government (Okotoni,2008; Akpan, 2020).

Kramer (2009), defined bureaucracy as a hierarchically arranged administrative system that exists in organisations contingent on the peculiarity of legitimate authority and separation of labour. Asonye (2015) in their input, portray the concept as the apparatus of governmental management which consists of specialists or unskilled workers who are under stringent hierarchical supervision and executing their authorised functions in a systematic method and reinforced by rules and regulations from their superiors. Eme and Onwuka (2010) view bureaucracy to entail a system of superintending official rapour that exists among persons, offices and procedures that government instrumentalises to implement its policies and programmes. Bureaucrats, according to Eme and Onwuka (2010) do not include political office holders; rather, they consist of civil and public servants. In the opinion of Ikenga (2016), Bureaucracy suggests a system that exists in both public and private organisations, whereby policies, responsibilities, system of authority and line of duty are structured and conscientiously but hierarchically devolved and shared among the various units that make up the organisation. The carrying out of these systematically but logically ordered functions according to Ikenga (2016), is further delineated among employed individuals whose roles, designations and ranks reflect the administrative structing of the operational system of the

organisation. In concurrence with the above definition, Obinze (2019) informed that bureaucracy entails a system where the human resource composition of an organisation, be it public or private in nature are saddled with the statutory responsibility of executing various tasks for the purpose of achieving the ultimate objective of the organization. In their separate input, Kolawole (2021), defined bureaucracy strictly from the perspective of public administration and government-related functions. In their definition, Kolawole (2021), impressed that bureaucracy involves the day-to-day implementation by employed civil/public servants, of the statutory mandate of any legitimate government in the form of policies, programmes, projects and schemes for the purpose of administering governance to the general public in the various Ministries, Departments, Agencies and other forms of public firms. In line with the thoughts expressed above by various scholars, this study defines bureaucracy as a systemic method that entails a strategic determination of mechanisms to execute rules, policies and services through the instrumentalisation of the human resource elements.

Bureaucracy in Nigeria

The origin of bureaucracy in Nigeria is traceable to the colonial era when the three major ethnic nationalities, in affiliation with other minority groups, provided the platform upon which the bureaucratic structures were built. The colonial administration, starting from 1906 formed government Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs), which functioned in the capacity of civil/public service organisations. This experience heralded the development and practice of bureaucracy in Nigeria. The colonial government entrenched and institutionalised a responsible, responsive and effective bureaucratic system in Nigeria. Hence, such development had translated to quality and people-driven public governance system. The colonial administration had achieved great successes in building a strong and viable bureaucratic system by restructuring and revamping the existing native administrative system in line with the ideals of westernisation as they pertain to public administration and governance. The Nigerian bureaucratic system over the years has passed through stages of reforms, prompting the creation of various Ministries, Departments and Agencies and other parastatals of government. Thus, these administrative structures of government have been rendering various aspects of social services to the people in the form of healthcare, education, good pipe-born water, access roads, etc. (Eneagu, 2021). The creation of MDAs of government in Nigeria further facilitated the formation of public establishments and industries which are expected to perform the dual functions of providing essential socio-economic services to the people at affordable rates and also existing as sources of revenue earning for the government. Hence, Nwoko and Offor (2024) posit that:

Nigeria's bureaucratic system comprises a body of full-time employees of government who are saddled with the constitutional task of executing statutory laws, policies and programmes of government, with the principal objective of ensuring that the will of the state is translated into the delivery of services to the citizenry. Usually, bureaucrats are operationally classified into civil and public servants. Civil servants are made up of employed government functionaries who work in government Ministries. Bureaucrats in government Ministries are directly responsible for laying the framework for translating policy statements of government into achievable objectives. (p. 90)

Over the years, the bureaucratic system in Nigeria has been functioning on various shades of administrative mediocrity and incompetence. Analytically, the characterisation of the bureaucratic system in Nigeria can be comprehensively understood from the angle of inherent proclivity to nepotism, cronyism, comradeship and favouritism, at the expense of merit. Other aspects of administrative incompetence prevalent in Nigeria's bureaucratic system include limited knowledge about tasks being performed, poor skill acquisition and deficient managerial ability. On the other hand, administrative mediocrity in the discharge of their statutory functions include poor commitment and lackadaisical

approach to work, as well as haphazard and unprofessional performance of tasks. As a consequence, the above administrative anomalies which characterise Nigeria's bureaucracy have consistently impacted negatively on the ability of civil/public servants in the various Ministries, parastatals and other forms of public enterprises to provide quality social services to the people (Mayowa, 2019).

Public Organisations

In order to achieve the basic statutory objective of providing essential social services to the people in a society, governments world over establish various bodies or establishments with a view to using them as avenues through which the citizenry can be made to maximally appreciate the impact of governance. Invariably, governments globally operate with a bureaucratic structure-the latter whose membership comprise full-time employed civil/public servants who carry out the day-to-day task of public governance and implementing government's policies and programmes. With a view to achieving a maximum objective of reaching out to the general public in a wider scope, governments usually elect to establish enterprises, industries or corporations that would provide essential services to the general public, free of charges or significantly subsidised rates. Hence, the establishment of public hospitals, public schools, hydro-power stations, waste management agencies, water boards, etc. is fundamentally purposed at providing free or affordable services to the people in the areas of healthcare, education, energy supply, waste disposal and water supply, respectively. Also, governments establish revenue boards with a sole motive of generating taxes from the numerous business activities that transpire within every geographically defined society. Thus, proceeds from taxation constitutes the mainstay of government's source of revenue (Osawe, 2015).

According to Olatunji (2013), public organisations refer to firms or industries established by governments to serve the purpose of providing essential services to the citizenry. In a similar perspective, Mayowa (2019), defined public organisations as establishments or institutions through which the government extends governance to its citizenry through service delivery. Also, Akpan (2020), posited that public organisations comprise avenues or channels through which the government meets the yearnings and aspirations of the people through service delivery. In a corroborative definition, though from a democratic perspective, Isodeke (2020), informed that public organisations exist as avenues through which the government keeps its own side of the social contract it entered with the masses by providing quality socio-economic services and benefits, in return for the people's mandate. In a similar but more explicit definition, Eneagu (2021) impressed that public organisations constitute the means by which the government intervenes by providing at affordable cost, those essential needs or services which ordinarily would have been beyond the reach or affordable capacity of majority of individuals in a society. Distinctively, Nwoko and Offor (2024), defined public organisations as outfits established by the government with a dual objective of providing essential social services to the people and also to generate revenues, needed for a sustained act of public governance.

Organisational Productivity

Organisational productivity is a term which refers to an overall assessment and determination of the level of effectiveness with regards to how an organisation utilises its resources to achieve set objectives and determined goals. Resources in this context refers to human, material and financial. Organisational productivity generally entails the ascertainment of the impact of the various efforts, strategies, schemes and methods deployed by an organisation to achieving its aims and objectives. The concept simply means the determination by an organisation of the actual amount of returns on investment. It denotes a discernible difference between resources committed to undertaking a task in an organization and the quantity of output realized. The difference in this context is usually expected to reflect the gain which is separated from the cost of investing in the performance of a task. Using a transactional analysis, organisational productivity represents the level of financial profit made after costs of executing a business or services in an organisation must have been separated. Also, using the transactional method of analysis, organisational productivity stands for the degree of value placed on the impact of the outcome of a service or services in an organisation. This pattern of determining or ascertaining organisational productivity

usually obtains in a scenario or condition where the value or profit for services rendered is not measured in monetary terms (Eneagu, 2021).

According to Ekpobari (2022), organisational productivity can be defined as the total sum of profit or successes an organisation records, over and above its investment capital. In their separate contribution, Ishaya (2023), informed that organisational productivity is a principle and strategy which every organisation pursues to ensure that the output of its operations is exceedingly greater than its operational costs. In the opinion of Akpan (2020), operational productivity reflects the idea that the human resource elements of an organisation must defend their relevance by ensuring that the financial and material resources invested into production or rendering of services are translated into maximum gains. Also, Mayowa (2019) stressed that “organisational productivity consists in all the indices that pertain to the triumph of the success stories of an organisation over its challenges and limitations” (p. 101).

A Critical Assessment of the Performance of Public Organisations in Nigeria vis-à-vis their Productivity Status.

The history of the existence of public organisations in Nigeria dates back to the colonial era when the British colonial administration created public corporations to provide essential social services. Some of the public organisations established by the British colonial government in Nigeria include the Nigeria Railway Corporation in 1955, Nigeria Customs Service (NCS) in 1891, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in 1958 but became fully operational on July 1, 1959 and the Royal Niger Company in 1879. The establishment of these public firms by the British colonial government in Nigeria, was primarily purposed at enhancing the delivery of social services and also to effectively intervene in improving the decadent infrastructural development status of the urban and rural communities in the colonially administered Nigerian state. The railway service played a very pivotal role in ameliorating the difficulties encountered in the transport of humans from one locality to the other and from one region to the other. As a colonial territory which was still considered developmentally very backwards, the train service was an advanced alternative to the other means of transport of humans and goods like water transport through the use of canoes and boats, bicycles, horses, camels and donkeys. During and shortly after the colonial era, automobiles were really in an extremely short supply, hence, the train service was really a very fertile alternative. Again, the railway services across the country during the colonial era contributed significantly to boosting the economic development of the Nigerian state. The train service remained a very safe, cheaper and dependable means for the conveyance of heavy goods and commodities on an inter-city, inter-region and inter-border basis. The British colonial government built and maintained a viable and responsible bureaucratic structure which ensured the effective administration of the mission and objectives of these public establishments (Nwakunor, 2015).

However, many years later, the legacies of the British colonial government with regards to achieving and consolidating socio-economic development for the Nigerian state through the establishment of public corporations were damned by obvious acts of bureaucratic mismanagement. Hence, Ogedi (2018), informed that problems of policy inconsistencies, political interferences, lack of managerial assiduity, indifferent dispositions, poor punctuality to duty and corrupt-tending dispositions by public servants constituted factors that contributed to the collapse of the economic legacies of the colonial administration in Nigeria. to this end, an empirical study carried out by Nwakudor (2015), at the Ebute-Metta Nigerian railway archives, reveals the extent of administrative impropriety of the Nigerian bureaucratic structure which is usually manifest in poor maintenance culture. The study by Nwakudor (2015), recounts a shared experience of a participant in the study, by name, Prof. Onyemaechi Eyeh. The latter in retrospect tried to establish a comparative analysis of the degree of dilapidation in the structures built by the colonial regime around that vicinity with its lively, colourful and actively functional outlook while growing up at Ebute Metta. Hence, “each time I passed by railway compound, I feel pains. I grew up in Ebute Metta so, I know what it was then, when Indians and a couple of white men were living here. Once a proud and bustling staff quarters, the place has been reduced to pock marked carcass of economic dislocation” (p. 5). According to Ogedi (2018), during the colonial experience in Nigeria, the Nigerian Railway Corporation

was chiefly instrumental in the movement of goods across borders. Also, the same could be said of the Post and telecommunication services which were optimally functional in previous times. However, the post-colonial operational capacity of these firms has declined over time.

The Ajaokuta Steel Company Limited (ASCL), also known as the Ajaokuta Steel Millin Industry is a public firm established by the Nigerian government in 1979, under the civilian administration of late Alhaji Shehu Shagari. The Ajaokuta Steel Company was erected on a 24,000 hectares of land (59,000 acres) and is considered the largest iron and steel industry in the whole of sub-Saharan Africa. The ASCL was established in Nigeria with various objectives, expected to culminate in overall economic development and transformation of the Nigerian state. First, ASCL was established to provide a fertile ground for the production of various structural forms and designs of steel and iron for the purpose of a faster pace of industrialisation of the country in various ramifications. Also, part of the objectives of the Ajaokuta steel company was aimed at intensifying accessibility to raw materials especially iron ores from the Itakpe mines in Kogi State. The objectives of ASCL also includes the discovery and training of skilled workers, hence the establishment of the Metallurgical Training Centre (MTC). In addition, it comprised part of the objectives of ASCL for the citing of the company to constitute an advantage to the host communities and the entire Kogi State by attracting other business investments like hotels, relaxation parks, health facilities, residencies, as well as attract the establishment of subsidiary firms to the state. Ultimately, the national objective for the setting up of the ASCL was to achieve a meaningful and economically dependable option of diversification away from oil and natural gas (Oluyole, 2017).

Unfortunately, after 44 years post-establishment of the Ajaokuta Steel firm, the company is yet to commence full operation. In 2022, the former Nigerian President, Muhammadu Buhari claimed that over \$400 million had been invested in rehabilitating the ASCL. In the same year, the government of Buhari paid an extra \$400 million for the resuscitation of the company. In the 2024 budget, the government allocated N4.45 billion for the same purpose of rehabilitating the Ajaokuta steel industry. Some of the factors responsible for the protracted delay in the rehabilitation of the Ajaokuta steel industry to commence full operation include, misappropriation of fund, bureaucratic red tape, policy inconsistency, political interference, political/bureaucratic corruption, among other issues (Natsa, 2024).

Organisational productivity in the public sector is supposedly measured by the degree of impact of the services rendered by public organisations or establishments on the masses. Productivity is said to have been achieved by public organisations if the feedback from the general public gives a nod to their services and performances. Conventionally, “public nod” in this context should reflect a maximum degree of people’s satisfaction over the quality of services rendered by public organisations. On the other hand, on the side of the government, organisation productivity in the public sector denotes the anticipated appreciable level of profitable returns recorded by the several enterprises or establishments set up by the government for the twin purposes of providing essential but quality services to the people and generating sufficient revenues to the public purse for the essence of executing the numerous tasks of public governance. Public organisations are said to be unproductive when they constitute a liability other than profit to the government that established them; when they operate below the expectation of the general public and when their operational existence becomes uncompetitive with their private sector counterparts (Ishaya, 2023). Hence, the ultimate criterion for testing and determining organisational productivity in public organisations, parastatals or firms, according to Ekpobari (2022) is through the following:

- i. The ability of public organisations to defend and justify the relevance of government with regards to social service delivery to the citizens of a country.
- ii. The ability of the executed social services to effectively transform into socio-economic development indices like employment generation, poverty reduction, quality healthcare delivery, high rate of physical infrastructural development, etc.
- iii. The capacity of public organisations to be reliable sources of revenue for the government.
- iv. The ability of public organisations to be resilient and thrive in a dynamic and competitive market economy.
- v. The ability of public organisations to experience a sustained level of growth and expansion.

However, in the typical Nigerian situation, productivity in public organisations has regrettably remained in a low and unsatisfactory manner. The low performance rating of public organisations in Nigeria has always reflected in the nature of services they render. Thus, poor and highly compromised service delivery usually characterise the operational output of public organisations in Nigeria. When compared with their counterparts at the international scene, public establishments in Nigeria obviously perform below expectation. According to the 2020 NNPC annual performance review, it was revealed that the performance rating of NNPC globally stood at 3.1/100, thereby ranking 85th out of 99 government-owned companies globally. Hence, this result reflected negatively in the productive capacity of the NNPC which showed that in the year 2020, the company's total revenue stood at N4.61 trillion, indicating a 23.8% decline from the N6.05 trillion the company recorded in 2019. It was also revealed that in that year, the total expenditure of NNPC subsidiaries nationwide was N4.52 trillion. With an 11.61% decrease in total crude oil production, it prompted the Federal Executive Council (FEC) to approve an additional \$1.5 billion for maintenance works to be carried out on NNPC's operational facilities. Beginning from the first quarter of 2024, the inability of independent marketers in the country to place orders for petroleum products, can be attributed to the backlog of debts by the NNPC. Hence, it was reported that the NNPC owes international refined oil traders to the tune of \$6 billion. Undoubtedly, this situation attests to the unproductive operational status of the NNPC (Ezugwu, 2024; Oxfam, 2024).

A Brief Review of the Factors that Limit the Capacity of the Bureaucracy to Achieve an Appreciable Degree of Productivity in Nigeria's Public Organisations

Civil/public servants constitute workers who are employed on a full-time basis to work in the various Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) of government in Nigeria. By extension and specifically as well, public servants comprise government employees who work in the various organisations or establishments set up by government to reach to the citizenry through service delivery and revenue generation. In contrast though, there are unarguable indicators to buttress the argument that public servants who constitute the bureaucratic structure of government have been failing in their statutory role of achieving a commendable level of productivity in Nigeria's public organisations. To this end, Akpan (2020) observed some factors which contribute to the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve productivity in Nigeria's public organisations and they include:

- i. Incompetence
- ii. Bureaucratic Red-tape
- iii. Non-Chalant Attitude to Work
- iv. Systemic Corruption (Political & Bureaucratic Corruption)
- v. Political Interference/Policy Inconsistency

Incompetence: According to Akpan (2020), the propensity for incompetence by public servants in the process of executing tasks in the public service, is most rampantly demonstrated in public establishments and firms. Further in their analysis, Akpan (2020) classified incompetence in two categories to include technical and administrative incompetence. Technical incompetence in this context entails the display of poor or limited knowledge about specific tasks, as well as the methods or strategies to execute them. Thus, in most Nigeria's public enterprises or firms, majority of employees in the production units of such establishments are not well-versed or skilled in the use of industrial equipment, tools and facilities. This, undoubtedly leads to poor or low production outputs and wastages. Administrative incompetence on the other hand, implies the lack of managerial skill or leadership qualities, necessary for sound policy making, controlling, directing and supervision of the entire affairs of the organisation, with a view to maximally realising organisational objectives.

Bureaucratic Red-Tape: According to Akpan (2020), this entails the rigorous processes required to obtain official approval for the implementation of statutory decisions and carrying out of official tasks. The stereotyped and long process of filling in paperwork, serial documentations, arduous task of obtaining licences and resort to the constitution of several committees before official decisions or policies are adopted have over time, constituted a bane on the activities of the Nigerian bureaucracy, with regards

to the management of public organisations in Nigeria. In short, the statutory requirement for excessive adherence to rules and official formalities by public servants contributes in a significant measure, to the low productivity status of public organisations in Nigeria.

Non-Chalant Attitude to Work: In their opinion, Akpan (2020) stressed that this constitutes a major problem of public servants in Nigeria. Hence, it has severally been observed that public servants in the various establishments of government approach their official duties with a high level of unseriousness, poor level of diligence and lack of deep commitment. Such, consequently have been known to contribute to low level of productivity in Nigeria's public organisations.

Systemic Corruption (Political & Bureaucratic Corruption): The morally-degenerate inclination of most public servants in Nigeria, according to Akpan (2020) has continued to impact negatively on the productive capacity of most public organisations in Nigeria. Over time, the act of embezzlement, misappropriations and other forms of corrupt-tending indulgences by public servants has grown endemic in Nigeria's public service. Hence, it has over the years, posed frustrating to the anticipated effective management of public organisations in the country. Again, this has usually taken the form of political/bureaucratic corruption- the latter involving an unwholesome collaboration between political office holders and public servants to embezzle, misappropriate or siphon funds meant for executing vital projects in the various government-owned establishments or enterprises. According to Odumakin (2020), the allegation levelled against a former Minister of Niger Delta and Niger Delta Development Commission, Sen. Godswill Akpabio by an erstwhile Managing Director of the Interim Management Committee of the Niger Delta Development (NDDC), Ms. Joy Nunie is a factual testament to the existence of political/bureaucratic corruption in public organisations in Nigeria. According to Ms. Nunie, Sen. Akpabio once persuaded her to raise a memo to fraudulently award emergency contracts for flood victims in the Niger Delta. Such situations and more, demonstrate the level of unwholesome and morally-degenerating synergy between political office holders and public servants to siphon funds meant for developmental projects in government-owned establishments. Unfortunately, this kind of trend has continued to be responsible for the low productivity status of public organisations in Nigeria.

Political Interference/Policy Inconsistency: In this context, Akpan (2020), impressed that often times, the activities of public servants in the various parastatals and establishments of government are indiscriminately impacted or in some occasions, upended by the actions and mis-actions of political office holders. These actions are often times, motivated and guided by personal interests and usually not in consonance with bureaucratic processes. Such negation of due processes by political office holders can emanate from either the occupiers of elective offices in the executive arm of government (President and state governors) or legislators at the federal and state levels. For instance, Isondeke (2020) observed that it constitutes an act of political interference on the activities of public servants when during legislative oversight functions by the National Assembly, the members resort to changing the budgetary figures sent to them by MDAs. Again, policy inconsistencies, usually occasioned by change of government can equally limit the capacity of the bureaucracy to achieve an admirable level of productivity in public organisations in Nigeria.

A Brief Assessment of the Port Harcourt Refining Company, Rivers State as well as its Productivity Status

The Port Harcourt Refining Company (PHRC) is an oil and gas public firm that was established by the Nigerian government to operate two oil refineries in the Alesa Eleme area of Rivers State. The two refinery centres in Port Harcourt are referred to as the Old Refinery (PH I) and the New Refinery (PH II). The former was commissioned in 1965 with a refining capacity of 60,000 barrels per day, while the latter was commissioned in 1989 with a production capacity of 150,000 barrels per stream day. The current Managing Director of the Port Harcourt Refining company is Mr. Ibrahim Onoja- the latter who assumed office in 2023. The major processing units at the Port Harcourt Refining Company include:

- i. Crude Distillation Unit (CDU) with 150,000 capacity
- ii. Vacuum Distillation Unit (VDU) with 150,00 capacity

- iii. Naptha Hydrotreating Unit (NHU) with 53,000 capacity
- iv. Catalytic Reforming Unit (CRU) with 33,000 capacity (Oladipo, 2021)

However, for decades now, the two refineries in Port Harcourt have been grossly underutilised, giving rise to them going outrightly moribund. The present moribund state of the PHRC can be attributed to a cumulative operational deficiency, lack of a sustained process of technical maintenance and managerial inefficiency. Over time, successive governments have voted in a lot of money for the rehabilitation of the refineries. In the year 2021, the Nigerian government invested \$1.5 billion for the total overhaul and modernised renovation of the refinery complex. Unfortunately, in spite of the obviously huge financial commitment in seeing to the comprehensive rehabilitation of the PHRC, no tangible improvement has so far been achieved. There have been series of postponements as to when the Port Harcourt Refining company would commence the rolling out of refined petroleum products to the final consumers. This condition has continued to perpetuate Nigeria's dependence on imported petroleum products. Hence, such has also impacted negatively on the country's foreign exchange as the naira continues perform poorly against foreign currencies like the us dollar, euro and pound sterling (Olawin, 2024).

For decades now, following the decadent state of the Port Harcourt Refining Company; following the unproductive status of the company, the federal government of Nigeria still spends money for the salaries, allowances and other zero-result maintenance expenses. It was reported that within the years 2020 and 2021, the federal government spent a total of N54.570 billion on salaries, wages and other employee benefits to workers who are unproductive by virtue of the redundant state of the company they are working in. Hence, it is on record that the Port Harcourt Refining Company did not make a single naira for the country between 2020 and 2021, yet such a huge sum was spent on salary and allowance payments. Critics have observed that such has been constituting the means through which the government accumulates financial leakages and wastages that have continued to eat up the country's national budget for decades. Hence, "in the face of very poor performance and large overheads, fixing Nigeria's unprofitable refineries to functional capacity has remained the promise of every administration since 1999..." (Jeremiah, 2021).

Critics have also observed that the cost of rehabilitating the loss-making Port Harcourt Refinery as well as the other two unproductive refineries of Kaduna and Warri is overwhelming and as such, impinges on the delivery of other vital social services in the country. To buttress the motion espoused above, Oyediji (2022), informed that the proposed and eventually released over \$3.5 billion was far more than the budgetary allocation for the health sector in Nigeria by successive governments for the years, 2009 to 2018. According to Oladipo (2021), incompetent technical staff, managerial incompetence, political/bureaucratic corruption, negligence, poor maintenance culture, bureaucratic delays in the implementation of official decisions, policy inconsistency, etc. constitute some of the factors responsible for the redundant and unproductive status of the Port Harcourt Refining Company.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the theory of Structural Functionalism. The theory of Structural Functionalism was developed in reaction to the pursuit to bring into existence, social symbols in understanding, interpreting and elucidating on the development, structure and workings of the society. Its aim was fundamentally concentrated on explaining social interactions, desires and systems in the society. Structural Functionalism is a social science theory which originated from the works of late 19th century sociologists and philosophers like Herbert Spencer, Emile Durkheim, Talcott Parsons and Robert Merton. The theory of structural functionalism sees the society as a constellation of interconnected parts which exist interpedently and must function collaboratively to solve the myriad of societal needs. It emphasises the existence of social institutions which are statutorily saddled with the task of societal maintenance (Harper, 2011).

In the field of Political Science and Public Administration, structural functionalism is a theory which explains the existence of inherent socio-economic needs and challenges in a society. The theory also unveils the existence of a lawfully established institution (the government), which is empowered by the

law that created it to allocate resources and administer solution to the diverse needs of the society. To maximally achieve the numerous tasks of administering the public, the government sets up various institutions, agencies and organs through which they are implemented. Also, the various tasks and function in these institutions have to be performed by a body of full-time employed individuals. Therefore, the theory of structural functionalism with respect to its relationship to the field of Political Science and Public Administration is anchored on the assumption that, while “structure” represents the various institutions, organs, agencies, parastatals and establishments which are created by the government to perform the multiple tasks of state administration and governance, “function” entails the numerous tasks of governance, needs and aspirations of humans in the society. The tasks of governance in this context which represents “functions” include healthcare, education, security, electricity supply, housing, food, employment opportunities, revenue generation etc. and must be performed by public servants who in the field of Public Administration are referred to as bureaucrats (Mayowa, 2019).

The theory of structural functionalism is relevant to this study as it will be instrumental in aligning the responsibilities of the structure which in the context of this study, pertains to the bureaucracy, with the functions which in this respect are associated with duties performed by public servants in the various public organisations.

DATA PRESENTATION

Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires

Distributed Questionnaires	%	Returned Questionnaires	%	Unreturned Questionnaires	%
420	100%	350	75%	70	25%

Source: Field work 2024

The table above indicates that four hundred and twenty (420) copies of questionnaires were distributed to 420 respondents. However, 350 questionnaires were successfully retrieved from the target respondents. This figure (350), represents 75% (in percentage), while the 70 unreturned questionnaires represent 25%. Thus, the 350 returned questionnaires were used for the study.

Gender distribution of respondents

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	255	73
Female	95	27
Total	350	100

Source: Field work, 2024

The table above shows that the gender distribution of respondents indicates that the male respondents are 225, which is 73%. On the other hand, the female respondents are 95, signifying 27.1%.

Marital status of respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Married	128	36
Single	222	64
Divorced	Nil	Nil
Total	350	100

Source: Field work, 2024

The above table also shows that among the 350 target respondents, 128 respondents are married, representing 36%. On the other hand, 222 respondents, representing 63.4% are single.

Educational qualification of respondent

Academic Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
SSCE	60	17
OND/NCE	90	26
HND/BSC	165	47
Postgraduate degrees	35	10
Total	350	100

Source: Field work, 2024

In the table above, the educational qualification information about the respondents indicates that the number of respondents with S.S, C.E. is 60, representing 17.1%, while 90 respondents, representing 26% have OND/NCE. On the other hand, 165 respondents, representing 47.1% have HND/BSC, while 35 respondents, representing 10% have postgraduate degrees.

Responses to Questionnaire Items by Respondents

Research Question 1: What are the factors responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve optimal productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company?

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Total SA/A	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total SD/D	Grand total
Involvement in corruption between political office holders and public servants	150 43%	165 47%	315 90%	20 6%	15 4%	35 10%	350 100%
Prolonged protocols and delays before policies and tasks are implemented	106 30%	104 30%	210 60%	69 20%	71 20%	140 40%	350 100%
Technical and administrative incompetence	141 40% ^x	106 30%	240 70%	50 14%	55 16%	105 30%	350 100%
Political interference	125 36%	100 27%	225 63%	80 23%	45 14%	125 37%	350 100%

Table 3.5. Source: fieldwork, 2024

The table above illustrates the reactions of respondents on the factors that are responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve maximum productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining Company. It showed that 315 respondents which represents 90% of the total population agreed with questionnaire statement that political/bureaucratic corruption constitutes a factor while 35 respondents which is 10% disagreed with the statement. Also, the table indicated that 210 of the respondents which translates to 60% of the respondents agreed with the statement that prolonged protocols and delays before policies and tasks are implemented constitutes a factor while 140 respondents which translates to 40% disagreed. Again, 240 respondents which constitute 70% agreed with the statement that technical and administrative incompetence are among the factors responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve productivity in PHRC while 105 respondents which mean 30% disagreed. Lastly, 225% of the respondents which translate into 63% agreed with the statement that political interference constitutes a factor while 125 respondents which represent 37% of respondents disagreed.

Research Question 2: What are the consequences of the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve optimal productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining Company?

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Total SA/A	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total SD/D	Grand total
Nigeria has continued to rely on imported refined petroleum product	190 54.2%	110 31.4%	310 85%	15 4%	25 11%	40 15%	350 100%
It has continued to impact negatively on the value of Nigerian currency	200 57%	108 31%	308 88%	21 6%	21 6%	42 12%	350 100%
It has given rise to a dwindling national revenue earning	113 32%	90 26%	203 58%	97 28%	50 14%	147 42%	350 100%

Table 3.6. Source: fieldwork, 2024

Under research question 2, the table above indicated that 310 respondents which translates to 85% agreed with the statement that part of the consequences of the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve productivity in the management of PHRC is that Nigeria has continued to rely on imported refined petroleum products, while 40 respondents which represent 15% disagreed. Also, 308 respondents which represent 88% agreed

with the statement that as a result of Nigeria’s continuous reliance on imported petroleum products, the value of naira is impacted negatively. However, 42 respondents which represent 12% disagreed. Lastly, 203 respondents which represent 58% agreed with the statement that among the consequences of the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve productivity in PHRC is the fact that national revenue earnings are depleting, while 147 respondents which represent 42P% disagreed.

Research Question 3: What strategies can be adopted to improve the capacity of the bureaucracy to effectively achieve productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company?

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Total SA/A	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total SD/D	Grand total
Increased emphasis on value re-orientation among workers at PHRC	126 36%	130 37%	256 73%	47 13%	47 13%	94 27%	350 100%
Private-public sector partnership in the management of PHRC	150 43%	100 27%	250 70%	40 11%	60 17.1%	100 30%	350 100%
Reduction in undue political interferences	150 43%	100 27%	250 70%	50 14.2%	50 14.2%	100 30%	350 100%

Source: fieldwork, 2024

under research question 3, 7256 respondents which represent 3% agreed with the statement that increased emphasis on value re-orientation among workers constitute a remedy, while 94 respondents, representing 27% disagreed with the statement. Also, 250 respondents, representing 70% agreed with the statement that private-public sector partnership is a strategy that boost the capacity of the bureaucracy to achieve maximum productivity in PHRC, while 100 respondents disagreed. Lastly, 250 respondents, representing 70% agreed with the statement that reduction in undue political interferences can constitute a strategy to improve the ability of the bureaucracy to achieve a maximum level of productivity in the management of PHRC.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Factors Responsible for the Inability of the Bureaucracy to Achieve Optimal Productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company.

The various positions of respondents on the factors responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve optimal productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining Company are reflected in table 3.5. Hence, the table represents the findings from this study. Therefore, this study, based on the opinion of majority of respondents in the field of study can confidently establish that political/bureaucratic corruption, bureaucratic red tape, technical/administrative incompetence and political interference, constitute the major factors responsible for the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining Company. The position of respondents in the field of study reflects experience in the larger Nigerian society and is also corroborated by other scholarly contributions and opinions. Hence, Akpan (2020) and Ekpobari (2022) have in their separate works, held the opinion that the unwholesome collaboration between political office holders and public servants to perpetrate corrupt acts, managerial incompetence, overstretched bureaucratic protocols and undue interferences on bureaucratic processes are some of the factors which cause redundancy and unproductivity in Nigeria’s public organisations.

Consequences of the Inability of the Bureaucracy to Achieve Optimal Productivity in the Management of Port Harcourt Refining Company

On the strength of the position of majority of respondents in table 3.6, this study establishes a finding to the effect that exclusive reliance on imported refined petroleum products, unfavourable exchange rate against the naira and dwindling national revenue generation, constitute the consequences of the inability of the bureaucracy to achieve a desired level of productivity in Port Harcourt Refining company. The finding from the field of study also reflects what obtains in the larger Nigerian society where the inability of the bureaucracy to effectively administer public organisations to be productive has left so many public

firms and establishments in Nigeria to be liabilities on the government instead of being sources of generating revenue for the government. The finding of this study in this context is buttressed by Oyediji (2022) who revealed that despite the fact that for decades now, Nigerian public refineries have not been functional, yet the Nigerian government in 2020, spent over N69 billion for payment of salaries of staff, working in moribund refineries. The same situation can be seen in other public organisations where the poor performances of public servants which usually lead to declining organisational productivity have always had consequences in poor revenue generation for the government.

Strategies to Improve the Capacity of the Bureaucracy to Effectively Achieve Productivity in Port Harcourt Refining Company

Based on the opinion and position of majority of respondents in table 3.7, this study unequivocally establishes a finding to the effect that increased emphasis on value re-orientation, public-private partnership and significant reduction in the level of undue interferences in the activities of public servants, constitutes potent measures and strategies to improve the capacity of the bureaucracy, with regards to achieving maximum productivity in the management of Port Harcourt Refining company. The same strategies if applied in the management of other public organisations in Nigeria would be relevant in achieving maximum productivity. The findings in the field of study is corroborated by some literature reviewed in the course of this study. Hence, Akpan (2020), impressed that a bureaucratic system where the principles of moral discipline, integrity and probity are observed, and where there is a committed effort to eliminate the morally-depraving act of political/bureaucratic corruption, is germane for the realisation of productivity in the administration of public organisations in Nigeria. Still in corroboration to the findings from the field of study, Isodeke (2020), posited that the restructuring of the management of Nigeria's public organisations to reflect public=private partnership will go a long way in improving the capacity of the bureaucracy with regards to achieving productivity in public organisations.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In Nigeria, as well as in other parts of the world, the administration of public organisations is embedded in the overall statutory duties that obtain in the public service. Hence, what constitutes the public service include the various fundamental tasks and responsibilities of governance like health, education, physical infrastructural development, security, human right protection, foreign relations, etc. Therefore, public organisations exist to serve as instruments through which the government performs its constitutional obligation of providing effective social services to the people. Invariably, the administration of these socio-economic to the Nigerian public is a function that is statutorily delegated to the bureaucracy-the latter which consists of a body of civil/public servants who are employed into the public service on a full-time basis. The dispensation of these aspects of essential social services for public consumption is usually anchored on the two objectives of rendering the services to the citizenry at a highly subsidised rate or outrightly free of charge in some situations and also with the intent of generating revenue for the government.

This study has extensively appraised and explored the impact of Nigeria's bureaucracy as it pertains to attaining an appreciable level of productivity as it administers public organisations. It was reliably observed in the course of this study that over time, public organisations in Nigeria have been performing below expectation, both in national and international rating standard. The poor-performing status of public organisations in Nigeria is usually demonstrated in low productive output. As a consequence, public organisations in Nigeria have consistently exhibited an obviously lack of capacity to be responsive to the socio-economic needs of the Nigerian public. Also, the unproductive nature of public organisations in Nigeria has severally been demonstrated in the inability of Nigeria's public establishments to be economically resourceful in the aspect of generating sufficient revenue for the government. In its stead, public organisations in Nigeria have turned to be redundant and liabilities, depending on the government for their existence. Hence, the unproductive nature of public organisations in Nigeria has been attributed to the inherent failings in the bureaucracy which include bureaucratic red tape, corruption and constant

political interferences in the functions of public servants. Therefore, this study rationalises that some elements of strategies need to be introduced into the Nigeria's bureaucratic system so as to achieve productivity in the management of public organisations.

Recommendations

- i. There should be a deliberate attempt at comprehensively overhauling of Nigeria's bureaucratic system to reflect public servants who would be morally upright; who would not indulge in political/bureaucratic corruption that has always characterised Nigeria's public service.
- ii. There should be public-private partnership as a restructuring strategy in the public service, with a view to enhancing the technical and managerial capacity of the bureaucracy. The ultimate objective would be to achieve maximum productivity in the running of public organisations in Nigeria.
- iii. Lastly, there should be evident limit to the rate at which political office holders interfere in the activities and functions of public servants. This has continued in the past, to frustrate the capacity of the bureaucracy to administer public organisations to achieve productivity. The curtailing of the undue interferences of political office holders on the activities of should reflect the limit to which inconsistencies in government policies vested interests of political office holders impinge on the functions of public servants.as it pertains to realising the objective of making public organisations maximally objective.

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